

THE IMPOSTER PHENOMENON IN WOMEN IN COLOR IN STEM

by

Tiffany Y. Yoo

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6904-7761

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Approved by:

Cherie Ichinose

Date:

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Dr. Ichinose, Department of Mathematics

Stacy Mallicoat

12/16/22

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

Abstract

Impostor Phenomenon (IP) -- the internal fear of being a fraud or an “impostor” plagues 18-24 year olds the most frequently at a rate of 46%, with 1 in 3 Americans suffering in general, according to a new survey by Money Penny. Although students may be successful in their studies, they have a hard time believing that their results were rightfully earned and attribute it to luck or oversight instead. There are minority groups of people within the science, technology, engineering and math (STEM) field that may suffer from an imbalance of representation and support, starting from a young age. Based on the lack of ethnic and female representation in history and textbooks, I hypothesize that an increase in minority representation will decrease IP. The aim of this study is to examine the contextual factors of IP, such as barriers that heighten Impostor Phenomenon, and explore ways to mitigate them. To aid in this exploration, we asked undergraduate STEM majors to participate in an online survey through Google Form, which includes the Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale (CIPS) to determine whether students indicated few, moderate, frequent, or intense Impostor Phenomenon. The survey records gender and ethnicity, which reveals the connection to the CIPS that women of color showed higher levels of Impostor Phenomenon. The statistical software, SPSS, analyzes the data collected through frequency distributions and t-tests. Overall, we report statistically significant differences between female and male student populations. Approximately 15% more female students reported higher scores of IP compared to males. Within underrepresented minority (URM) groups, females also show higher levels of Impostor Phenomenon, confirming that women in STEM most commonly suffer from the Impostor Phenomenon.

Introduction

The phenomenon known as Impostor Phenomenon is one that is common among the STEM field. Feeling like a fraud when conceptually difficult ideas are being taught is understandable. However, there are certain groups of people within the STEM field that may suffer from an imbalance of representation and support, starting from a young age. Those who do choose to pursue a career in STEM may notice certain groups of people falling behind more than others. This possible pattern is what will be exposed through the research that will be conducted, specifically among undergraduate STEM majors. The hypothesis is that women of color in STEM suffer from the Impostor Phenomenon the most. Furthermore, the study will examine the contextual factors of this phenomenon to explore ways to mitigate the Impostor Phenomenon.

Literature Review and Theoretical Model

From secondary education all the way to higher education, women in STEM can find it difficult to be motivated or confident in their efforts and skills. There is an overall low concentration of both women and minorities in STEM relative to the overall workforce and those who hold STEM degrees (Collins et al., 2020, p. 162). Having white male-dominated historical figures, teachers, and classrooms, women of color may find it difficult to find inspiration or self-confidence in their own skills to be successful. The context of their education can likely lead to an occurrence called the Impostor Phenomenon, which is an internal fear of being a fraud or an “imposter” (Feenstra et al., 2020). Although they may be successful in their studies, they have a hard time believing that their results were rightfully earned and instead attribute it to luck or oversight. The focus of this literature review is to determine if and why this Impostor Phenomenon occurs more frequently in women of color who are in the STEM field.

Secondary Education

In the American education system, many women go to school with the notion that men are the great figures that are making history. Across all STEM subjects, women are taught that men like Einstein and Newton are just naturally born geniuses who made these monumental discoveries. Harvard's Implicit Project shows that people associate STEM with men and conclude that since the most successful scientists are men, perhaps only men can successfully pursue science (Kahn & Ginther, 2017). This kind of feat seems unachievable, especially when history tells you that these great people are nothing like you. Setting up the classroom to model after these people can be a great discouragement to young women who are under the impression that they are not capable of such accomplishments. In their minds, they may not even begin to think of pursuing the STEM field as a possibility. Thus, when deciding what paths to take, the road may seem very narrow or even impossible. However, if women do decide to follow their passions in STEM, they may still be hindered with the doubts of how they could contribute or succeed in their efforts. Being in a male-dominated field, their classrooms may be overwhelmingly disproportionate in terms of gender, which can be discouraging and isolating. In the journal, *Consequences of Stereotype Threat and Imposter Syndrome: The Personal Journey from STEM-Practitioner to STEM-educator for Four Women of Color*, one woman of color describes early signs of Impostor Phenomenon inside and outside the classroom:

I experienced Imposter Syndrome in the classroom as early as high school, often being the only person of color and the youngest in an accelerated, advanced mathematics and computer science curriculum... The more advanced courses became, the less I would see students that I associated with socially or who looked like me. I started to wonder why the friends that I had the most in common with socially were not in these classes with me. Even though I continued to build on my STEM skills throughout my young adult life, I

often found myself feeling as if I wasn't 'one of them.' For example, even though I considered myself good at 'doing' mathematics, I did not see myself 'being' a mathematician or computer scientist. On the flip side, I experienced Imposter Syndrome outside the class as well – I wasn't 'one of them' either. I later referred to this as 'superman syndrome', having extraordinary talents but hiding them to fit in. In high school, I would even go so far as to hide the fact that I was in the most advanced "nerd" classes. I would often downplay my intelligence using humor. Based solely on these early experiences, I would proclaim that one consequence of Imposter Syndrome and stereotype threat for women of color is feeling as if they are living a double life, and not wholly true or belonging to either." (Collins et al., 2020, p. 163-164).

The academic and social pressures inside and outside the classroom can have a great impact on the way students feel about themselves in regards to their passions in STEM. Having these experiences as the foundation for their career can only hinder or discourage them from believing in themselves to achieve great things, increasing their Impostor Phenomenon. The Superman Syndrome is a phenomenon that lacks research but warrants more consideration on how it contributes to the Impostor Phenomenon.

Higher Education

When entering the STEM field as an undergraduate, the environment will only resemble the secondary education environment, with more white male professors and classmates. The classes will only be bigger and the expectations will only be higher. The journal, *"I Don't Know Why They Make It So Hard Here": Institutional Factors and Undergraduate Women's STEM Participation*, evaluates the ways in which gender stereotypes interact with elements of institutional culture to play a role in women's STEM-major selection and persistence

(Lindemann et al., 2016, p. 222). One of the cultures that played a factor into the intersectional marginalized identity experienced by women of color in STEM was large class size, which is common in public universities. A former chemistry major recalled:

My lecture, which was like 200-300 plus [people]...I was one of three black girls in that class. And it was more of a pride thing and not going up to the professor because it's kind of like, oh well, you're that black girl from the inner city school, of course you're going to need help. You know what I mean?...It's kind of like, oh, she's a black girl, what did you expect?...[I]t's still that whole fear of being in a science class and having it be filled with predominantly white males, and then there are a few white women there, and then it's kind of like being the minority in that class and being afraid to raise your hand because you might be 'the dumb one.' It was that whole fear. (Lindemann et al., 2016, p. 233-234)

Choosing to pursue the STEM route is one thing, but being in the process of pursuing it is another. The challenges that women of color face in order to reach their goals can seem a lot higher than most people. Thus, phenomena like the "stereotype threat" and "Impostor Phenomenon" can only flourish in these types of environments. However, there seems to be a lack of specific research on the different types of environments in the higher education system. This one example of a large class size doesn't encompass all the factors that play into the development of the Impostor Phenomenon.

Post-Graduate Life

Due to the Impostor Phenomenon, women professionals within the STEM career may feel over evaluated by colleagues and administrators. In the journal, *Barriers and assistance for female leaders in academic stem in the US*, a survey was given with 134 responses from women

in active STEM leadership positions. When asked what the biggest challenge was for women in the leadership track, 20 of the women was gender bias of some form or another: “Systematic devaluing of women faculty in department” or “Not being seen as possessing hard skills because of my gender and attractiveness” or “Having to be twice as competent to be viewed as good enough” (McCullough, 2020). One woman wrote that “I’ve been flat out told by people ‘I wouldn’t have consulted you on this project if I knew you were a woman. But you seem okay, so we can work together.’” (McCullough, 2020). This kind of treatment and environment can make women doubtful of the true nature of their competencies. Although they have gone through the rigorous education process of earning a degree, they still have to face these kinds of obstacles and discriminations that only foster the Impostor Phenomenon. However, the statistics gathered in this study for women leaders in STEM only recorded 20 out of the 134 people who responded. This can lower validity and strength in the argument, so more responses from women of color in STEM leadership must be collected. In the article, *Contextualizing the impostor “syndrome”*, research suggests that such a lack of representation and lower compensation elicit doubts about women of color’s suitability for these occupations and positions (Feenstra et al., 2020). This line of research suggests that these institutions that are traditionally occupied by white men increase their susceptibility to feel like an “impostor”.

The school and work environment, the social and academic pressures, and the gender bias can shape the perception of one’s capabilities, especially for women of color in STEM. Through tools like the survey in McCullough’s journal and the Clance Impostor Scale, which “assesses components of the phenomenon such as ideas about self-doubt and achieving success by chance” (French et al., 2008), people are realizing how more and more women are experiencing the Impostor Phenomenon throughout their academic career. Instead of focusing heavily on

characteristics of the individual, future research is necessary to examine contextual variables at the societal, institutional, and interpersonal levels that shape an individual's impostor feelings (Feenstra et al., 2020).

Methodology

The problem statement is to determine if and why this Impostor Phenomenon occurs more frequently in women of color who are in the STEM field, specifically in the area of mathematics. There is an overall low concentration of both women and minorities in STEM relative to the overall workforce and those who hold STEM degrees (Collins et al., 2020, p. 162). Having white male-dominated historical figures, teachers, and classrooms, women of color may find it difficult to find inspiration or self-confidence in their own skills to be successful. The context of their life, including the school and work environment, the social and academic pressures, and the gender bias, can shape the perception of one's capabilities and lead to an occurrence called the Impostor Phenomenon, which is an internal fear of being a fraud or an "imposter" (Feenstra et al., 2020). This topic is important because not enough is being done to tackle the issue of this widespread phenomenon, and more research needs to be done around the context of this situation. Instead of focusing heavily on characteristics of the individual, future research is necessary to examine contextual variables at the societal, institutional, and interpersonal levels that shape an individual's impostor feelings (Feenstra et al., 2020). This problem occurred to me when I was going into my junior year of college, taking my most important and rigorous major classes. I saw myself undergo a tremendous amount of mental health issues mainly due to my academic performance. This was the first time I realized how severe my Impostor Phenomenon was, to the point where I wanted to drop out because I didn't think I'd ever make it. I am still going through this process of understanding my thoughts and

trying to undo whatever lies my mind is telling me. Then, I realized that I wasn't alone in this struggle when my classmates would share their struggles with me. As I heard people's stories, I realized a common theme: they were all women of color. I understand that some research and observations have already been done about how women of color may have a more intense experience with the Impostor Phenomenon. However, the research question to be explored is: among undergraduate STEM majors, do women of color experience higher levels of the Impostor Phenomenon?

Research Aims and Objectives

There has been a lack of research on how the contextual factors of the STEM field are potentially inducing the Impostor Phenomenon in women of color. The aim of this thesis is to gain an understanding on why women of color may be experiencing this phenomenon, especially in the STEM field, and what changes can be made to prevent this from spreading. The objective of this research is to

1. Determine if women of color in STEM experience Impostor Phenomenon more intensely by comparing survey results between different genders and ethnicities.
2. If so, determine what the root cause of the Impostor Phenomenon is by focusing specifically on the contextual factors.
3. Examine what preventative measures can be implemented in order to stop this widespread phenomenon from occurring.

The result of this research ultimately creates clarity for how this Impostor Phenomenon is a result of certain contextual factors and instigate real measures that can make this phenomenon far less common than it currently seems to be. The short-term objective is to spread awareness on

the reality of the Impostor Phenomenon in the STEM field. The long-term objective is to implement effective changes that will help mitigate this phenomenon.

Data Collection

I conducted a 27-item survey through Qualtrics using quantitative research methods to compile information regarding a student's personal background and beliefs as they relate to the Impostor Phenomenon. Students' levels of the Impostor Phenomenon were measured by self-reports using the Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale (CIPS). The online survey instrument included two open-ended questions which will be used for future qualitative analysis. The CIPS was designed to measure the concept that individuals are successful by external standards but have an illusion of personal incompetence. The CIPS consists of 20 statements that measure and assess the frequency of impostor feelings and experiences encountered by participants. Answers to the items were based on a 5-point scale: 1 = "not at all true", 2 = "rarely," 3 = "sometimes," 4 = "often," and 5 = "very true". The sum of the points gave scores indicating the level of the Impostor Phenomenon: less than or equal to 40 indicated few impostor feelings, between 41 and 60 indicated moderate impostor feelings/experiences, between 61 and 80 indicated frequent impostor feelings/experiences, and greater than or equal to 81 indicated intense impostor feelings/experiences. The instrument was chosen in part due to the high internal consistency ($\alpha = .84 - .96, .92$) (Chrisman et al., 1995; Clance, 1985, Peteet et al., 2015). The questions are as follows:

1. I have often succeeded on a test or task even though I was afraid that I would not do well before I undertook the task.
2. I can give the impression that I'm more competent than I really am.
3. I avoid evaluations if possible and have a dread of others evaluating me.

4. When people praise me for something I've accomplished, I'm afraid I won't be able to live up to their expectations of me in the future.
5. I sometimes think I obtained my present position or gained my present success because I happened to be in the right place at the right time or knew the right people.
6. I'm afraid people important to me may find out that I'm not as capable as they think I am.
7. I tend to remember the incidents in which I have not done my best more than those times I have done my best.
8. I rarely do a project or task as well as I'd like to do it.
9. Sometimes I feel or believe that my success in my life or in my job has been the result of some kind of error.
10. It's hard for me to accept compliments or praise about my intelligence or accomplishments.
11. At times, I feel my success has been due to some kind of luck.
12. I'm disappointed at times in my present accomplishments and think I should have accomplished much more.
13. Sometimes I'm afraid others will discover how much knowledge or ability I really lack.
14. I'm often afraid that I may fail at a new assignment or undertaking even though I generally do well at what I attempt.
15. When I've succeeded at something and received recognition for my accomplishments, I have doubts that I can keep repeating that success.
16. If I receive a great deal of praise and recognition for something I've accomplished, I tend to discount the importance of what I've done.

17. I often compare my ability to those around me and think they may be more intelligent than I am.
18. I often worry about not succeeding with a project or examination, even though others around me have considerable confidence that I will do well.
19. If I'm going to receive a promotion or gain recognition of some kind, I hesitate to tell others until it is an accomplished fact.
20. I feel bad and discouraged if I'm not "the best" or at least "very special" in situations that involve achievement.

Responses

I received 140 responses from undergraduates majoring in STEM from all ethnicities and genders. Then, I analyzed the patterns of the results to come to a conclusion of whether or not women of color in STEM experience Impostor Phenomenon at higher rates. In order to reveal students' feelings of the Impostor Phenomenon, this study used statistical analyses that included frequency distributions and t-tests. The variables included the following: overall Clance Impostor Phenomenon Scale score and variables associated with the Impostor Phenomenon, such as luck or error. Descriptive statistics reveal different levels in self-reported beliefs. These descriptive statistics examined the behavior of specific student self-identified subgroups: gender and ethnicity. Gender was categorized as male and female and ethnicity was categorized as URM and non-URM. URM consists of American Indian or Alaska Native, Black or African American, Hispanic or Latino, Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander, and Mixed Race. Non-URM consists of Asian and White.

Results

Overall, the data showed that females showed higher levels of Impostor Phenomenon compared to males. Within URM groups, females also showed higher levels of Impostor Phenomenon, solidifying the fact that women in STEM most commonly suffer from the Impostor Phenomenon.

In Table 1, of the sample, 78.6% reported frequent or intense IP experiences. Approximately 15% more female students reported higher scores of IP than males. This difference was statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 2.808$, $df = 99.220$, $p = .003$) with equal variance not assumed. 81.7% of URM students reported high scores of IP, which was significantly higher than the Non-URM students ($t = 2.125$, $df = 137.935$, $p = .018$). In Table 2, Question 11 shows that 39.3% of the sample reported “Somewhat True” or “Very True”. 23% more URM students reported higher levels of IP than non-URM. This difference was shown in Table 3 to be statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 2.694$, $df = 137.459$, $p = .004$) with equal variance not assumed. Question 17 shows that 75% of the sample reported “Somewhat True” or “Very True”. 25.5% more female students reported higher levels of IP than males. This difference was shown in Table 3 to be statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 3.499$, $df = 133$, $p = <.001$) with equal variance assumed.

Of the male sample, 70% reported frequent or intense IP experiences. Approximately 14% more URM students reported higher scores of IP than non-URM. This difference was not statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 1.015$, $df = 48$, $p = .158$) with equal variance assumed. In Table 4, of the female sample, approximately 85% reported frequent or intense IP experiences. Approximately 2% more URM students reported higher scores of IP than non-URM. This difference was statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 2.200$, $df = 83$, $p =$

.015) with equal variance assumed. In Table 5, Question 10 shows that approximately 53% of the female sample reported “Somewhat True” or “Very True”. Approximately 27% more URM students reported higher levels of IP than non-URM. This difference was shown in Table 6 to be statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 2.405$, $df = 82.563$, $p = .009$) with equal variance not assumed. Question 11 shows that 49.4% of the female sample reported “Somewhat True” or “Very True”. Approximately 25% more female students reported higher levels of IP than males. This difference was shown in Table 6 to be statistically significant at an $\alpha = .05$ level ($t = 2.181$, $df = 83$, $p = .016$) with equal variance assumed.

Discussion

The results of the study showed that women in underrepresented minorities in the STEM field experience more intense Impostor Phenomenon feelings or experiences than others. These findings are consistent with other research results demonstrating a relationship between the Impostor Phenomenon and gender (Trefts, 2019). While some found a correlation in generation status, other studies showed a correlation in racial identity (Peteet, et al., 2015), which is consistent with the results of this study.

There is more work to be done. This study showcased the continued reality that women of color face when it comes to the Impostor Phenomenon. Future research must include contributing factors associated with why this phenomenon may occur more in women of color. Quantitative analysis such as correlation, and multiple regressions can be used to identify the most significant variables that contribute to the Impostor Phenomenon. Thus, through the discovery of these variables, more solutions can be found to diversify the STEM field in hopes that more decisive solutions in schools and government can be made.

There were several limitations in this study. First, the survey analysis depended on the information provided by the students themselves. It also depended on the students' truthfulness and eagerness to participate in the study. Responses could have been influenced by thoughts and feelings at the time the survey was distributed (two-weeks before final examinations).

CSUF is doing an excellent job at combating the Impostor Phenomenon in women of STEM through opportunities, such as Project MISS, SMART Girls and CNSM Summer STEM Academy. Project MISS, which stands for Mathematics Intensive Summer Session, is a supplementary enrichment program intended to strengthen college-bound young women's foundational understanding of mathematics and to eventually increase the population of female-identifying students who choose careers in STEM. SMART GIRLS, which stands for Sisters in Mathematics and Academic Relations in Teaching, is a campus club that supports women in STEM advance in their academic career. The CNSM Summer Stem Academy is a two-week program that provides incoming CNSM undergraduates with the opportunity to explore the different parts of STEM.

Conclusion

Not enough research is being done nor is there enough awareness being spread to tackle this serious issue of the Impostor Phenomenon. This hindrance in the STEM field may be a huge roadblock to the advancement of the STEM career. In order to help expand the opportunities that STEM can offer, this research will help uncover if certain groups are struggling or even unwilling to pursue this avenue of STEM. By hearing the personal experiences of undergraduate students pursuing the STEM field, people can utilize their stories to make improvements for the betterment of the future in STEM.

Tables & Figures

Chart 1:

Chart 2:

Table 1:

Gender & Ethnicity Frequency

		Few IP Characteristics	Moderate IP Experiences	Frequent IP Experiences	Intense IP Experiences	n	M	sd
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)			
Final Imposter Syndrome Score	Sample	2.9%	18.6%	50.7%	27.9%	140	3.0357	0.76253
	Male	4.0%	26.0%	54.0%	16.0%	50	2.82	0.74751
	Female	1.2%	14.1%	49.4%	35.3%	85	3.1882	0.71538
	URM	1.4%	16.9%	45.1%	36.6%	71	3.1690	0.75566
	non-URM	4.3%	20.3%	56.5%	18.8%	69	2.8986	0.75039

Table 2:

Question		Not at all True				Very True	n	M	sd
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)				
(11) At times, I feel my success has been due to some kind of luck.	Sample	16.4%	20.0%	14.3%	25.0%	14.3%	140	2.74	1.263
	Male	22.0%	18.0%	10.0%	30.0%	20.0%	50	3.08	1.482
	Female	12.9%	20.0%	17.6%	23.5%	25.9%	85	3.29	1.387
	URM	14.1%	15.5%	9.9%	25.4%	35.2%	71	3.52	1.462
	non-URM	18.8%	24.6%	18.8%	24.6%	13.0%	69	2.88	1.334
(17) I often compare my ability to those around me and think they may be more intelligent than I am.	Sample	5.0%	9.3%	10.7%	25.0%	50.0%	140	3.68	1.387
	Male	10.0%	14.0%	18.0%	24.0%	34.0%	50	3.58	1.357
	Female	2.4%	7.1%	7.1%	24.7%	58.8%	85	4.31	1.035
	URM	4.2%	9.9%	14.1%	22.5%	49.3%	71	4.03	1.195
	non-URM	5.8%	8.7%	7.2%	27.5%	50.7%	69	4.09	1.210

Table 3:

T-test - Gender & Ethnicity

	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)
Gender			
Score	2.808	99.220	.003
Question 17	3.499	133	<.001
Question 18	2.862	133	.002
Question 20	2.617 ¹	93.943	.005
Ethnicity			
Score	2.125 ¹	137.935	.018
Question 8	2.490 ¹	137.551	.007
Question 10	2.484 ¹	137.991	.007
Question 11	2.694 ¹	137.459	.004

¹ equal variances not assumed

Chart 3:

Table 4:

Ethnicity Within Gender Frequency

		Few IP Characteristics	Moderate IP Experiences	Frequent IP Experiences	Intense IP Experiences	n	M	sd
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)			
Final Imposter Syndrome Score	Male	4.0%	26.0%	54.0%	16.0%	50	2.82	0.74751
	Female	1.2%	14.1%	49.4%	35.3%	85	3.1882	0.71538
	URM Male	0%	23.1%	61.5%	15.4%	26	2.9231	0.62757
	Non-URM Male	8.3%	29.2%	45.8%	16.7%	24	2.7083	0.85867
	URM Female	0%	14.3%	35.7%	50.0%	42	3.3571	0.72655
	Non-URM Female	2.3%	14.0%	62.8%	20.9%	43	3.0233	0.67218

Table 5:

		Not at all True				Very True	n	M	sd
		(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)			
(10) It's hard for me to accept compliments or praise about my intelligence or accomplishments.	Male	10.0%	14.0%	24.0%	26.0%	26.0%	50	3.44	1.296
	Female	4.7%	21.2%	21.2%	20.0%	32.9%	85	3.55	1.277
	URM Male	7.7%	7.7%	30.8%	23.1%	30.8%	26	3.62	1.235
	Non-URM Male	12.5%	20.8%	16.7%	29.2%	20.8%	24	3.25	1.359
	URM Female	4.8%	14.3%	14.3%	21.4%	45.2%	42	3.88	1.273
	Non-URM Female	4.7%	27.9%	27.9%	18.6%	20.9%	43	3.23	1.212
(11) At times, I feel my success has been due to some kind of luck.	Male	22.0%	18.0%	10.0%	30.0%	20.0%	50	3.08	1.482
	Female	12.9%	20.0%	17.6%	23.5%	25.9%	85	3.29	1.387
	URM Male	15.4%	11.5%	15.4%	38.5%	19.2%	26	3.35	1.355
	Non-URM Male	29.2%	25.0%	4.2%	20.8%	20.8%	24	2.79	1.587
	URM Female	11.9%	19.0%	7.1%	19.0%	42.9%	42	3.62	1.497
	Non-URM Female	14.0%	20.9%	27.9%	27.9%	9.3%	43	2.98	1.205

Table 6:

T-test - Ethnicity Within Gender

	t	df	Sig. (1-tailed)
Ethnicity Within Female			
Score	2.200	83	.015
Question 8	2.488 ¹	82.999	.007
Question 10	2.405 ¹	82.563	.009
Question 11	2.181	83	.016
Ethnicity Within Male			
Score	1.015	48	.158
Question 7	1.335 ¹	43.735	.094
Question 10	0.992 ¹	46.548	.163
Question 11	1.323 ¹	45.431	.096

¹ equal variances not assumed

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